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EXPERIENCES OF ACADEMICALLY STRUGGLING LEARNERS: BASES FOR INTERVENTION PROGRAM IN SCIENCE

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Abstract

The qualitative research aimed to determine the learning experiences of academically struggling learners as bases for intervention program in science on Grade nine learners' of Buayahon-Bantay National High School, Santa Barbara, Iloilo. The study utilized descriptive approach, employing purposive sampling, structured interview, and thematic analyses process. The study identified three main themes which are Literacy, Behavior and Environment for Learning (LABEL). These three main themes served as bases for crafting the Championing Learners in Struggles in Science (CLASS): An Intervention Program for Literacy for Academics, Behavior and Environment for Learning (LABEL). The intervention program addresses the concern of learning experiences as to the literacy, behavior and environment for learning. The implementation of the program is a collaborative effort of teachers and parents at home for continuous learning. Learning materials are contextualized and suited to the level and pacing of the learners. Results and monitoring of the implementation are supported with scores and observation notes of both teachers and parents.

Keywords: Learning Experiences, Literacy, Behavior, Learning Environment, Intervention

1. Introduction

The center of science education emphasizes effective learning where students are active learners in a conducive environment facilitated by competent teachers. The quality of teaching significantly impacts students' innovative learning experiences, challenging them to think critically and integrate knowledge, skills, attitudes, and experiences. Lopes (2010) highlights the importance of instructional approaches in shaping students' learning encounters, suggesting the need for varied teaching practices and further study to enhance students' competences.

In the Philippines, the shift to online classes due to the pandemic has posed challenges for schools, particularly in public institutions, affecting students' learning experiences. Issues such as gadget availability, internet stability, budget constraints for technology, and education quality have emerged (Arinto, 2019). Robosa (2021) identifies teacher challenges during the pandemic, particularly in handling students who struggle to meet academic requirements, often resulting in below-average

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grades. Department of Education (DepEd) directives mandate remedial intervention for academically challenged students, emphasizing the need for schools to craft intervention programs to support struggling learners and prevent dropouts (Fuente, 2019).

In classrooms, especially in public schools, the diverse learner population necessitates high-quality teaching strategies tailored to individual needs, particularly for academically struggling students.

In a classroom environment, particularly in many public schools, the diversity of learners serves as tangible proof that teachers need to employ high-quality and effective teaching strategies. Such strategies should address the individual needs of every student, particularly those who face challenges in passing subjects or have academic ratings below the average. Academically struggling learner or those who struggle to pass the subject are visible in every classroom.

Learning experiences affected by different factors were mentioned and became the avenue to conduct the study. The researcher wanted to pull out the concept of improving the quality of learning from the experiences of academically struggling learners.

With all the aforementioned and with the limited conducted study about the learning experiences of academically struggling learners the study was conducted to serve as benchmark for other possible researchers about learning experiences of students in science that may become bases for intervention program.

2. Methodology

The study employed a descriptive approach and utilized purposive sampling to select participants. A researcher-made interview schedule was used to collect qualitative data. Thematic analysis, specifically the reflexive thematic approach by Braun and Clarke (2008), was employed to analyze the data. Ethical considerations were prioritized, with participants given a letter of permission and consent outlining the study's purpose.

Seventeen participants took part in the study, comprising eight academically struggling learners, eight parents, and one science teacher. Inclusion criteria for participants included, grade nine students enrolled in the 2022-2023 academic year, obtaining an academic rating below the passing rate, and awareness of their classification with poor literacy and numeracy levels.

Participants received a letter inviting them to participate in the study, along with a letter of consent for the interview and a copy of the interview schedule. Face-to-face interviews were scheduled, with academically struggling learners interviewed individually on different days, parents met during the card day or through home visits, and the teacher interviewed after all learner interviews were completed.

Data analysis involved thematic analysis, specifically reflexive thematic analysis, which explores patterns of meaning in the qualitative dataset. Themes were constructed to provide a deeper understanding of the learners' experiences and behaviors in science education. The research aimed to address the study's objectives by examining the lived experiences of the participants and understanding how they perceive and engage with science learning.

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3. Results and Discussion

The study identifies three main themes: **literacy, behavior, and learning environment**, which emerged from the narratives of academically struggling learners. The Intervention Program was formed based on the narratives of the three main themes.

The common learning experiences of academically struggling learners were difficulty in note taking, poor vocabulary & comprehension and less participation in classroom activities. They also have behavioral problem that affect their ability to study.

On the other hand, academically struggling learners, as observed by parents and teachers, have no focus, and have short attention span. Aside from these, they have poor comprehension and need to ask their teacher to repeat the lesson.

Moreover, the teacher observed that learners have short attention span and have poor literacy & numeracy levels and difficulty in taking-down notes.

The parents and teachers have involvements with struggling learners in learning science. Parents become learning facilitators at home while teachers provide simple task assessment suited to learners' level. Teachers also employed peer teaching and acted as psychological motivator.

Learners manage the learning experiences through following themes; peer learning, asking the teacher to repeat the discussion and slowdown in speaking, which could be considered as teacher factor, and drill & practice.

Out of the different sub-themes presented that answered the statement of the problems, three main themes are **literacy, behavior, learning environment**. These themes were the bases for crating the intervention program entitled, **CLASS: An Intervention Program for LABEL**.

CLASS: An Intervention Program for LABEL is designed to support academically struggling learners in science education. The acronym "CLASS" stands for Championing Learners in Struggles in Science and "LABEL" stands for Literacy, Behavior, and Environment for Learning, representing the three major themes of the program. The word "championing" signifies the aim of making learners excellent and the best, reflecting the mantra of the Schools Division of Iloilo.

According to Department Order No. 12, s. 2021, schools are required to implement intervention and remediation activities based on the specific needs of learners, as identified through assessments conducted over the past two quarters. Remediation is directed towards learners who have struggled to pass a subject for two consecutive years.

The CLASS: An Intervention Program for LABEL learning materials addresses the key findings of the study, focusing on literacy skills such as reading, spelling, comprehension, and note-taking. Additionally, it targets learner behavior and the learning environment to enhance overall learning outcomes.

The specific objectives of the program are as follows:

1. **Improving Literacy Skills:** Utilizing teaching and learning materials to enhance vocabulary, comprehension, and note-taking skills, thereby addressing struggles in learning science.

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2. **Effective Learning Activities:** Developing and implementing activities that are performance-based to motivate learners' participation and engagement in classroom discussions and activities.
3. **Continuous Learning at Home:** Implementing interventions for continuous learning at home, encouraging parental involvement in the learner's educational journey, thus creating a conducive environment for continuous learning.
4. **Behavioral Counseling:** Conducting behavioral counseling sessions at the end of each quarter to monitor and evaluate learners' behavioral aspects, providing necessary support and guidance.
5. **Monitoring Literacy Status:** Regularly monitoring the literacy status of learners through record keeping of assessment results and observation notes, both by teachers and parents at home.

By addressing these objectives, the program aims to enhance the overall learning experience and outcomes of academically struggling learners in science education.

Based on DepEd Order No. 12, s. 2021, the CLASS intervention program is tasked with conducting intervention and remediation activities tailored to the unique needs of learners as identified through assessments. The program focuses on several key areas to achieve its objectives:

1. **LAC Sessions for Crafting Learning Materials:** These sessions involve creating modules and activity sheets aimed at enhancing literacy skills, including vocabulary and comprehension.
2. **Enhancing Note-taking Skills:** Through teaching strategies in class discussions, the program aims to improve learners' note-taking abilities.
3. **Activities Promoting Active Participation and Peer Learning:** Various activities are designed to encourage student engagement and collaboration with peers.
4. **Behavioral Counseling:** Continuous support is provided to learners through behavioral counseling sessions aimed at addressing behavioral issues.
5. **Guidelines for Continuous Learning at Home:** The program includes guidelines for parents to support continuous learning at home, monitoring parental involvement, and observing learners' experiences.

Teachers play a crucial role in identifying struggling learners and implementing the program, while parents are encouraged to enhance their involvement in their child's learning journey. Overall, CLASS aims to empower academically struggling learners in science education and support their success.

4. Conclusion

The learning experiences of academically struggling learners leads to the identification of parents' involvement in the continuous learning at home and the involvement of teacher as the prime mover of the teaching-learning process. Moreover, the exploration of these learning experiences shows the learners' management in order to cope up in class considering the different aspects to consider which were all presented through main themes.

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By addressing the three identified main themes (Literacy, Behavior and Learning Environment) and empowering both parents and teachers to support academically struggling learners, the intervention program (CLASS: An Intervention Program for LABEL) aims to create a collaborative and supportive learning environment that fosters student success and well-being. Moreover, by acknowledging learners' agency in managing their learning experiences, the program seeks to promote resilience, confidence, and academic growth among students facing academic challenges.

5. Recommendation

The study's findings shed light on the learning experiences in science education for learners, parents, and teachers. It emphasizes the importance of addressing areas needing improvement and the active involvement of parents and teachers in the learning process. LAC Sessions provide a platform for teachers to discuss concerns, while contextualized learning materials aid in comprehension for parents. Consistent monitoring tracks learners' progress, with parents encouraged to actively engage in their child's learning journey. The intervention program is suggested for broader implementation, potentially integrated into School Improvement Plans, with a focus on addressing classroom issues collaboratively for holistic learner development.

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